

THE ROLE OF LOCAL APPLICATION OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN BIOLOGICAL TEACHING

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Maintaining its dominance in the modern educational process

The upcoming traditional education provides for the organization of general educational training of students and the activities of students as passive listeners, holds. Middle-level students are involved in the organization of educational work your student's independence is ignored, learning. Activities are supervised by the teacher.

Therefore, the transformation of students into full-fledged subjects of their educational activities, the humanization of pedagogical relations and democratization, the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the process of teaching biology in order to increase the effectiveness of training the need has arisen.

ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the role of using pedagogical technologies at the local level in the teaching of biological sciences, work in small groups, cluster, case technologies.

Quality teaching of the educational process such as providing literature and advanced pedagogical technologies includes a number of tasks. Successful pedagogical technologies in the educational process special methodological knowledge for biology teachers to apply and skills required in teaching practice have methodological training.

There are three levels of pedagogical technology:

1. General methodological degree.
2. Special methodological degree.
3. Local (modular) degree.

Biology teacher organizes your student's learning activities In order to improve the teaching and learning process, It is advisable to apply at the local (modular) level in the lum phase.From domestic pedagogical technologies in teaching biology "Keys", "Cluster", "Venn Diagram",

"Brainstorm", "Small group work", "Chain of terms", "Terminology sheet", quick games use various forms of game exercises. Problems of teaching biology course the use of "Keys" gives high efficiency.

Case-"Cases" - case studies originating from English, process or

means a situation. It is advisable to use this method mainly in the process of studying the lessons of evolutionary content. In particular, case studies in teaching topics

such as "The Origin of Man" and "The Origin of Life on Earth" help students to determine the most appropriate

needed to solve a problem situation. In the case, the teacher must be able to

problem situation on the topic and the age of the students. Instead of using this case

study in the classroom and depending on the level of difficulty, it is important that

students can properly target it to small groups or the whole class. The teacher's

preparation of each thematic activity, such as the Student Handout and Teacher

Handout, has a significant impact on the lesson.

Using Clusters in teaching Biology to systematize and consolidate students'

knowledge plays an important role. Cluster in translation from English means cluster.

This local technology allows students to understand the relationship between the

ideas, theories, laws and concepts that they have mastered and are learning develop

analytical and critical thinking skills trains.

Cluster creation is done in the following order:

1. Write a term or section on a topic written in the middle.

2. Signs of the concept written in the middle are branched. These networks are defined by separate forms. In the presence of concepts specific to them, further branching will continue and the appearance of "grapes" will appear.

There are equally few students in the class using the cluster divide into groups

to achieve them the didactic purpose of the lesson. Once the execution order is

needed, they are within the allotted time. The best and most well-structured cluster

is determined by summarizing and protecting the cluster they created winners

will be rewarded. This means that the pedagogical system, which is successfully

used in the education system of the developed countries of the world and

develops in didactics.

Know that technology is human-centered, learner organization and management of

his activities, his attitude to the individual, something traditional that dominates the

modern education system updating the content of education and organizing the

educational process.

The importance of each subject in the teaching of science has been repeatedly

recognized in connection with its radical change.

Heart with two

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